

Identification of Chronic Urticaria Subtypes Using Machine Learning Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic urticaria (CU) is a heterogeneous disease with distinct phenotypes and endotypes. Disease subtypes can be identified by machine learning (ML) algorithms, but this approach has not yet been used in CU.

Objective: To explore subgroups of CU patients by unsupervised cluster analyses using ML algorithms.

Methods: We performed a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using ML-based k-means clustering applied to 3 continuous and 15 categorical clinical and routine laboratory features in 337 CU patients (165 with isolated chronic spontaneous urticaria [CSU], 25 with isolated chronic inducible urticaria [CIndU], and 147 with CSU+CIndU).

Results: We identified four clusters of CU patients. Cluster 1 (n=25) consisted of only and all patients with isolated CIndU. Assignment to cluster 2 (n=142) was primarily driven by high IgE levels and absence of antinuclear antibodies (ANA) and thyroid peroxidase antibodies (IgG-anti-TPO). Cluster 3 (n=128) patients had the highest rate of angioedema as well as IgG-anti-TPO and ANA positivity, 77.3%, 39.8%, and 52.3%, respectively. Patients in cluster 4 (n=42) had high rates of comorbidity, especially hypertension and diabetes mellitus.

Conclusions: This study provides proof of concept that cluster analyses with ML algorithms can identify distinct CU patient subgroups, which are similar to real life subtyping, i.e. CSU vs. CIndU and CSU with autoantibodies and low IgE vs. no autoantibodies and high IgE. Our results encourage the use of this approach in multicenter studies with more patients and variables and exploring the relevance of the clusters identified.

Highlights box

What is already known about this topic?

Disease subtypes can be identified by machine learning algorithms, but this approach has not yet been used in chronic urticaria.

What does this article add to our knowledge?

Cluster analyses can identify meaningful and distinct groups of patients with chronic urticaria.

How does this study impact current management guidelines?

Cluster analysis using unsupervised machine learning algorithms identifies 4 distinct subtypes of chronic urticaria, which are similar to real life subtyping. This approach may be used to better characterize relevant and distinct pathomechanisms of CU subgroups.

Keywords: Chronic urticaria, phenotype, endotype, cluster analysis, machine learning

Abbreviations:

ANA: antinuclear antibodies

CU: Chronic urticaria

CIndU: Chronic inducible urticaria

CSU: Chronic spontaneous urticaria

ML: Machine learning

PC: Principle component

PCA: Principal component analysis

TPO: Thyroid peroxidase

INTRODUCTION

Chronic urticaria (CU) comes as chronic spontaneous urticaria (CSU) and chronic inducible urticaria (CIndU) which consists of physical urticarias (symptomatic dermographism, heat and cold urticarias, delayed-pressure urticaria, solar urticaria, and vibratory angioedema) and nonphysical urticarias (cholinergic urticaria, contact urticaria, and aquagenic urticaria) (1).

Across its types and subtypes, CU is a heterogeneous disease that has different phenotypes with distinct clinical characteristics and different endotypes with distinct underlying pathophysiological mechanisms (2, 3). The current treatment strategy in CU uses a “one size fits all” trial and error approach. The development and use of endotype-specific and targeted treatments require a better understanding of CU subgroups, of subgroup-specific pathogenic drivers, predictors, biomarkers, and response to treatment.

In CU, distinct endotypes appear to be linked to certain phenotypic features. Type IIb autoimmune CSU, for example, is characterized by high rates of low IgE levels, and type I autoimmune CSU is linked to higher rates of response to omalizumab (4). On the other hand, certain clinical features of CU have been shown to link to individual endotypes. Comorbid autoimmune disorders, for example, point to type IIb autoimmunity, whereas comorbid allergic disorders appear to be linked to type I autoallergic disease (5, 6). For some features, the phenotype/endotype-alignment is stronger when they are present in combination rather than alone. Low IgE and elevated IgG-anti-TPO, each alone, are weakly linked to type IIb autoimmune CSU. When they are present in combination, that link is a strong one (4, 6). It may, therefore, be possible that subgroups of CU patients exhibit distinct phenotypic disease signatures that can point to differences in what drives their condition and in their response to treatments. Cluster analyses can help to detect such subgroup signatures.

Cluster analysis is a popular unsupervised machine-learning (ML) method for discovering previously undetected data patterns. In selecting groups, i.e. clusters, the primary aim is to minimize intra-group variance while simultaneously maximizing inter-group variance (7). This method was well shown identifying distinct clusters of asthma phenotypes before. It was possible to identify 5 clusters of distinct clinical asthma phenotypes from The Severe Asthma Research Program cohort that differed in lung function, age of asthma onset and duration, atopy, sex, symptoms, medication use, and health care utilization (8). Further studies also supported that this approach can exhibit differences in clinical response to treatments (9, 10). As of now, no study has attempted to identify CU subtypes with this method. Here, we performed a proof-of-concept study to test if cluster analysis using ML algorithms can identify subgroups of CU patients based on clinical and routine laboratory characteristics.

METHODS

Patients and variables

We retrospectively analyzed the medical charts of a cohort of 431 CU patients followed-up between 2018 and 2020 at the Dermatology Clinic of the Kayseri City Hospital, which is an Urticaria Center of Reference and Excellence (UCARE) since 2019. Of all patients, 94 were missing one or more of the cluster variables and were excluded. The final sample included 337 patients. Thirty-two of these patients were children and adolescents under the age of 18, 165 (49%) had isolated CSU, 25 had isolated CIndU (7.4%) and 147 (43.6%) had both CSU and CIndU (see figure E1 in the Online Repository).

We subjectively selected clinical characteristics and biomarkers, and reduced the number of variables by eliminating clinically irrelevant ones by expert advice from the 70 variables in the original dataset. We excluded the variables that would be irrelevant for the current analysis and had no proven connection with CU before (such as smoking habits). We selected clinical characteristics that are not subject to treatment effects such as disease activity, quality of life and treatment response. Thus, consecutive records of urticaria activity score and/or urticaria control test were excluded. As ongoing and previous treatment histories of the patients were not patient characteristics, they were also excluded. When selecting the biomarkers, we first considered all biomarkers that had previously been shown to be relevant for CU, especially CU endotype. The dataset provided information about antinuclear antibody (ANA) titers and staining patterns, and baseline IgE, C-reactive protein (CRP), erythrocyte sedimentation rate, and IgG-anti-TPO levels. At the end, biomarkers that had least missing data and the ones that were least affected by independent factors (like infections) and most stable over time were included. Antinuclear antibody and IgG-anti-TPO levels were converted to binary files. Three continuous variables, which were age in years, disease duration since diagnosis in months and baseline serum total IgE levels (IU/mL), and 15 categorical variables, which were gender, presence of angioedema, presence of asthma, hypertension, diabetes, hypothyroidism, any psychiatric illness, any rheumatological disease, atopic dermatitis (these were the most prevalent comorbid diseases and all included to the analysis as separate variables), IgG-anti-TPO positivity (>0.34 U/mL), family history of urticaria, presence of CSU, presence of CIndU, presence of triggers (we only included the most prevalent aggravating factors, i.e. stress, foods and infections, and did not include CIndU subtype specific and definite triggers), and ANA positivity constituted the final set of clinical and laboratory features that were analyzed.

Statistical analysis

Data Preprocessing

Data were analyzed using the Python environment, the `sklearn` library (11) was used for statistical analyses, and `matplotlib` (12), `seaborn` (13) libraries were used for statistical data visualization.

To accommodate cleaned versions of data to be processed for subsequent steps, we performed preprocessing where patients with any NaN (Not a Number) values in their feature variables were excluded. After data preprocessing, the number of patients with data where all 33 features available was 337. Before proceeding to the next step, we also normalized data using a standard scaler approach, i.e. transforming into standardized features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance. Note that Principal Component Analysis (PCA) basically tries to get the features with maximum variance and is very sensitive to the scaling of the variables. If there are high magnitude features in the dataset, variance becomes higher which skews the PCA towards high magnitude features. During our experiments with other scaling functions such as max-min scaler (scales and translates each individual features in the range of 0 – 1), robust scaler (scales and translates each feature based on the interquartile range) or max-abs scaler (scales and translates each individual feature such that the maximal absolute value of each feature will be 1.0) (14), we observed higher sum-squared error distances (for robust scaler), lower than average silhouette scores for some of the clusters (for max-abs scaling) and no clear elbow point matching with silhouette coefficient method (for max-abs scaling). Moreover, the optimal number of clusters using silhouette coefficient methods given by some of those methods (e.g. with max-min and max-abs) were too high (number of clusters=9) based on expert analysis.

Dimension Reduction

Patient medical data include several data points (variables), and it is reasonable to assume that not all of them are relevant for patient clustering. As the use of high numbers of variables can make the ML model complex and harder to interpret and can also cause overfitting, we used PCA. This reduced the number of input features for our clustering algorithm and helped to avoid the so-called *curse of dimensionality* phenomenon, i.e. the challenge to obtain statistically significant results when data are analyzed in high-dimensional spaces, which in turn creates data sparsity. As a matter of fact, we observed higher sum-squared distances and lower silhouette coefficient scores during clustering when no PCA techniques were utilized. We used python's *sklearn* library to perform PCA. The main advantage of using PCA in our analysis is to create a balance between information retention and model simplification, i.e. to explain as much as possible of the total variance in the dataset, with a minimal number of factors. Additionally, principal components can also be used to interpret the association with original features as they represent the input data variability via linear combination of input data features.

PCA reduced the 33 original features (3 continuous and 30 categorical encoded features after one-hot encoding of 15 binary categories) to 10 principal components (PCs), by maintaining 70% of the information provided by all components (Figure 1). In other words, the variance captured in the data was 70% with 10 PCs, which provides a reasonable balance between model complexity and interpretability (15). Note that each PCs can also be interpreted by their eigenvalue. We also experimented with 16 PCs corresponding to %90 variance in data as input to k-Means clustering algorithm which resulted in lower silhouette scores and higher sum square error distances due to the detrimental effect of higher dimension. For this reason, we

decided to proceed with 10 PCs in our analysis to obtain a good balance between the input dimensions to the clustering algorithm and the obtained evaluation metrics.

k-Means Clustering

The main goal of this study was to classify patients based on their clinically observed features and serum biomarkers as described above. With the available data, we used the k-Means clustering approach to group the patients and label the clusters accordingly. The reasons for this approach include its ability to generate clusters with different shapes and sizes, its scalability to large datasets, its simple implementation, and guaranteed convergence (e.g. in case of Euclidean distance metric) features.

Before applying clustering to principal components of the reduced dimension dataset, we performed the Hopkins test to verify the spatial randomness of the transformed dataset and that our dataset has clustering tendencies. We conducted the Hopkins test using the Python's `pyclustertend` library (16). Hopkins statistical test basically assesses the clusterability of the dataset. The input to the test is the input dataset and the sampling size (selected as the size of the dataset). It allows us to guess if the dataset is uniformly distributed. If the score is near to 0 it means the data is not uniformly distributed, On the other hand if the Hopkins score is too high, e.g. above 0.3, it means the data is uniformly distributed and clustering can not be a useful solution. Hopkins test results showed a p value of 0.24, indicating that the selected data points indeed have clustering tendencies.

The first step in clustering with k-Means is to select the appropriate k centroids and, by this, the number of clusters. Initially, we selected random locations for k centroids. The second step is the assignment step, where each patient is assigned to the nearest centroid. The third step

is to recalculate the means of centroids based on new assignments. The final step is to alternate between the second and third step until convergence where assignments no longer change. To determine the number of clusters to be used in the k-means algorithm, we used the silhouette coefficient and the elbow method on dimensionally reduced data. Figure 2A shows the silhouette coefficient values with varying numbers of clusters. Silhouette coefficient is an internal measure to assess how similar an object is to its own cluster (cohesion) compared to others (separation) and ranges between -1 and 1. Figure 2B visualizes the elbow method results on the sum of square distances from each point to its assigned center for a range of different k values. The elbow method indicated k=4 to be the elbow point, the best number of clusters, the same as obtained with the silhouette coefficient (Figure 2A). Guided by the domain knowledge and cluster evaluation metrics (using the results of both Figure 2A and Figure 2B) to make an elaborate attempt of grouping the data, we decided to classify data into k=4 clusters as it gives a good balance between the number of clusters and the selected evaluation metrics. To calculate silhouette values, we used squared-euclidean distance as the measure for both cohesion and separation. The silhouette diagram for k=4 shows that the thickness plots (i.e. the widths of shapes) of the two twin clusters (both clusters 2, 3 and clusters 0, 4) are more or less similar and hence are of similar sizes. At the same time, most of the points in the clusters have above 0.39 silhouette values and extend beyond the red dashed line (with an average silhouette score close to 0.2) indicating that the clusters are well separated. Figure 2D also shows the scatter plot of the four clusters distributed over the reduced dimensions of PCA1 and PCA2 which in total explain 20% variance created by the data. We can observe from this figure that cluster distributions over the first two components appear to be distinctly identified.

After cluster label assignments to each patient with the above described analysis, accordingly using the 33 features of the original dataset, comparisons between clusters were performed either with Pearson Chi-square test or Kruskal-Wallis H-test for the categorical and continuous variables, respectively. *p-value* <0.05 was considered significant. Pairwise comparisons of the clusters were performed with *post-hoc* analysis using Bonferroni's correction.

RESULTS

Cluster analyses with machine learning-based algorithms identify four distinct subgroups of patients with chronic urticaria

ML-based k-means clustering with PCA silhouette analyses and use of the elbow method of dimensionally reduced data showed 4 clusters of CU patients, with a homogeneous balance between the clusters and the selected evaluation metrics (Figure 2). Clustering analyses with PCA resulted in more meaningful clusters than without and supported the positive impact of reduced dimensions and cluster number identified. Cluster characteristics and comparisons identified clinically distinct patient subgroups (Table 1).

The most important variables that drove cluster assignment were CSU (Yes/No), CIndU (Yes/No), gender, angioedema, comorbidities (hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and hypothyroidism), serum IgE level, ANA (Yes/No), and IgG-anti-TPO (Yes/No). Of the 18 clinical and laboratory variables used, the four identified clusters did not differ in only four, i.e. age, presence of triggers, rheumatological disease and asthma (Table 1).

Cluster 1: The “CIndU only” cluster

Cluster 1 (n=25, 7.4%) was the smallest cluster and consisted of all and only CIndU patients who did not have comorbid CSU (Table 1, Figure 3). Of all clusters, cluster 1 patients had the highest age [median 42 (28-51) years], the shortest duration of disease [12 (5-96) months], and the lowest IgE levels [74.6 (35.1-188.5) IU/mL]. Most patients (72%) had at least one triggering factor such as stress, foods, or infections, in addition to their CIndU subtype-specific trigger.

Cluster 2: The “high IgE” cluster

Cluster 2 (n=142, 42.1%) was the largest cluster (Table 1, Figure 3). All patients had CSU and half of them had comorbid CIndU. Cluster 2 patients, on average, had the highest IgE levels [132 (56.4-271.5) IU/mL], the highest rate of comorbid atopic dermatitis (7.7%), and the lowest rate of ANA and IgG-anti-TPO positivity (1.4 and 4.2%, respectively).

Cluster 3: The “autoimmune” cluster

Cluster 3 (n=128, 38%) was the second largest group, and 92% of patients were women, the highest rate of all clusters (Table 1, Figure 3). All patients had CSU, and more than half also had CIndU (56.3%). Three of four patients (77.3%) had angioedema, the highest percentage of any cluster. Cluster 3 patients also had the lowest IgE levels (84.2 IU/mL) of any CSU cluster and

the highest rates of IgG-anti-TPO and ANA positivity across all clusters (39.8% and 52.3%, respectively).

Cluster 4: The “high comorbidity” cluster

Cluster 4 (n=42, 12.5%) was the second smallest group (Table 1, Figure 3). All patients in this group had CSU, and comorbid CIndU was rare (14.3%). Cluster 4 patients were the youngest, 38 (25.8-46.3) years on average, and most patients had angioedema (73.8%). The defining characteristics of patients in this cluster, the high comorbidity cluster, were their high rates of hypertension (74%), diabetes mellitus 62%) and hypothyroidism (38%), each at least twice as high as in any other cluster.

DISCUSSION

This study provides proof of concept that the use of unsupervised ML algorithms can cluster patients with CU, a very heterogeneous disease, into four different and distinct subtypes. Three of these four clusters are remarkably similar to how patients with CU are classified in real life, i.e. as having CIndU or CSU as their primary form of CU and, in the latter, as having autoimmune or autoallergic CSU (Figure 3).

Cluster analysis has long been used to subtype different allergic diseases, especially asthma (8, 17). Until today, only one study used this method to classify CU patients, with a different objective than ours. In their retrospective cohort analysis, *Ye et al.* used K-medoid

clustering analyses of medication scores with the aim of estimating remission rates and prognostic factors of relapse in different treatment requirement clusters of CU (18).

The most interesting and important finding of our study is that all patients with isolated CIndU were clearly separated and grouped in cluster 1, whereas all of the CSU patients fell into other clusters. This is in line with the current guideline-recommended classification of CU. It shows that patients with different CIndUs are more similar to each other than to patients with CSU. The ML algorithm-driven identification of isolated CIndU patients based on their clinical and laboratory characteristics supports the current understanding that specialized care and treatment strategies are needed in patients with CIndU (19).

Two of the three CSU clusters, cluster 2 and cluster 3, clearly differed in their serum biomarker profile, gender ratios, disease duration and angioedema positivity. All of these are CSU aspects that urticaria specialists turn to, in routine clinical practice, when they aim to establish if patients have autoimmune type IIb CSU or autoallergic (autoimmune type I) CSU. The key features of cluster 2, ANA and anti-TPO positivity and low IgE, are well recognized markers of autoimmune type IIb CSU (6, 20) as are high rates of concomitant autoimmune diseases (21). Some of these biomarkers, such as total IgE, are also predictors of response to treatment (22, 23). In short, the algorithms applied in this study came to a very similar grouping of CU patients as compared to that based on specialist assessment, but they did not require or use expert knowledge. This provides proof of concept that the identification of meaningful subgroups and their analysis are possible with ML-based algorithms.

Cluster 4 is an interesting, not previously recognized subgroup of CU, defined by high rates of comorbid hypertension, diabetes mellitus and hypothyroidism. Cluster 4 patients should

be further investigated for how they differ in their disease risk factors, predictors, pathogenic drivers and treatment responses from patients in other clusters.

In this study, we limited the algorithms employed to the use of only 18 disease features. We expect that ML-based investigations with more features can provide even higher granularity in subcategorization of CU patients. This may, eventually, result in signatures that allow for reliable predictions of the course of CU and the response to specific treatments.

Being a proof-of-concept study, our present work has several strengths and inherent limitations. As for the latter, our study 1) is single center and lacks replication in another patient cohort, 2) only used selected clinical characteristics and relevant biomarkers rather than a wider range of different variables, and 3) used the k-means clustering method, which is highly dependent on initial centroid locations. The latter requires careful examinations to select optimal initial values and the hyper-parameter k value to be specified by the user. Its strengths include its novel unsupervised and ML-based approach and the sizable number of patients analyzed. Still, we believe the predictive role of these results are unclear and require validation in a larger sample of patients with chronic urticaria.

Taken together, the results of our study demonstrate that cluster analyses can identify meaningful and distinct groups of patients with chronic urticaria. This suggests that ML-based algorithms can be used to establish patient signatures, which may then be used to better characterize relevant and distinct pathomechanisms of CU subgroups. This, in turn, will allow us to better manage CU, by optimizing the use of available treatments and guiding the development of new and better ones.

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TABLES

Table 1. Cluster analyses with machine learning-based algorithms identify four distinct subgroups of patients with chronic urticaria.

	All patients n=337 (100%)	Cluster 1 n=25 (7.4%)	Cluster 2 n=142 (42.1%)	Cluster 3 n=128 (38%)	Cluster 4 n=42 (12.5%)	P- value*
CSU; n (%)	312 (93)	0 (0) ^a	142 (100) ^b	128 (100) ^b	42 (100) ^b	<0.001
CIndU; n (%)	172 (51)	25 (100) ^a	69 (49) ^b	72 (56) ^b	6 (14) ^c	<0.001
Angioedema; n (%)	198 (59)	12 (48) ^{a,b}	56 (39) ^b	99 (77) ^c	31 (74) ^{a,c}	<0.001
Median age in years (IQR)	39 (28-49)	42 (28-51) ^a	3 (29-48) ^a	41 (29-50) ^a	38 (26-46) ^a	0.481
Female gender; n (%)	237 (70)	16 (64) ^{a,b}	71 (50) ^b	117 (92) ^c	33 (79) ^{a,c}	<0.001
CU duration; months (IQR)	24 (9-76)	12 (5-96) ^{a,b}	36 (12-96) ^a	18 (9-50) ^b	24 (6-120) ^{a,b}	0.039
Family history; n (%)	72 (21)	6 (24) ^{a,b}	20 (14) ^b	37 (29) ^a	9 (21) ^{a,b}	0.03
Triggering factor(s); n (%)	262 (78)	18 (72) ^a	115 (81) ^a	95 (74) ^a	34 (81) ^a	0.474
IgE; IU/mL (IQR)	102 (38-226)	75 (35-189) ^{a,b}	132 (56-272) ^a	84 (23-167) ^b	93 (26-203) ^{a,b}	0.005
IgG-anti-TPO positivity; n (%)	68 (20)	4 (16) ^{a,b,c}	6 (4.2) ^c	51 (40) ^b	7 (17) ^a	<0.001
ANA positivity; n (%)	82 (24)	2 (8) ^{a,b}	2 (1.4) ^b	67 (52) ^c	11 (26) ^a	<0.001
Hypertension; n (%)	37 (11)	5 (20) ^a	0 (0) ^b	1 (1) ^b	31 (74) ^c	<0.001

Diabetes mellitus; n (%)	45 (14)	3 (12) ^a	12 (9) ^a	4 (3) ^a	26 (62) ^b	<0.001
Hypothyroidism; n (%)	64 (19)	6 (24) ^{a,b}	19 (13) ^b	23 (18) ^a	16 (38) ^{a,b}	0.004
Psychiatric disease; n (%)	115 (34)	10 (40) ^{a,b}	57 (40) ^b	30 (23) ^a	18 (43) ^{a,b}	0.014
Rheum. disease; n (%)	57 (17)	5 (20) ^a	28 (20) ^a	17 (13) ^a	7 (17) ^a	0.538
Atopic dermatitis; n (%)	12 (4)	0 (0) ^{a,b}	11 (8) ^b	1 (1) ^a	0 (0) ^{a,b}	0.006
Asthma; n (%)	57 (17)	5 (20) ^a	22 (16) ^a	20 (16) ^a	10 (24) ^a	0.584

CSU: chronic spontaneous urticaria; CIndU: chronic inducible urticaria; IQR: interquartile range;

CU: chronic urticaria; IgE: serum total IgE level; TPO: thyroid peroxidase; ANA: antinuclear

antibodies. **P-value* from Kruskal-Wallis H-test or Pearson Chi-square analysis between the 4

clusters. Each superscript letter (a,b,c) denotes pairwise comparisons between clusters and shows

that the columns with the same letters in a line do not differ significantly from each other at the

0.05 level.

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: After performing PCA, we reduced 33 original features to 10 principle components (PCs), maintaining 70% of provided information by all components.

Figure 2: Machine learning-based cluster analyses identify four distinct subgroups of patients with chronic urticaria. Silhouette analysis (A) and the elbow method (B) show that four is the optimal number of clusters for categorizing patients with chronic urticaria. The silhouette diagram for 4 clusters shows that the vast majority of the patients belong to the cluster they were assigned to and fit the cluster characteristics (C) and that the clusters are well separated (D). Visualization of the clustered data over the reduced dimensions of PCA1 and PCA2 using scatter plot (D) shows that cluster distributions over the first two components can be distinctly identified.

Figure 3. The four chronic urticaria clusters. The clusters are plotted according to the characteristics of how chronic urticaria (CU) is classified in real life as having chronic inducible urticaria (CIndU) or chronic spontaneous urticaria (CSU), and, for the latter, as having autoimmune or autoallergic CSU. Cluster 1 is the “CIndU cluster”, cluster 2 is the “high IgE cluster”, cluster 3 is the “autoimmune cluster” and cluster 4 is the “high comorbidity” cluster. Surface areas represents the size of the population distributed to each cluster (*ANA: antinuclear antibodies; IgE: serum total IgE level; TPO: thyroid peroxidase*)